

Large Mammal Survey for KPE for the period Jan – March 2025

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Standard names from the IUCN Red List have been used, and the status is according to the 2025 list (<https://ewt.org/red-list/>).

The last column indicates species included in the 2010 survey (MTPA (2010). *KwaMandlangampisi* Protected Environment Five Year Management Plan 2011-2016. Unpublished report, Mpumalanga Tourism and Parks Agency, Nelspruit, South Africa.). Records from 11 observers are included in this list.

The most interesting observations:

- Bushpig was not recorded in 2010 but is now a pest. Other new observations include Bat-eared Fox, Brown Hyaena, Large Spotted Genet, Scrub Hare, Rock Hyrax, Yellow- and other species of Mongoose, Polecat, Porcupine, Southern Reedbuck, and Steenbok.
- The number of species has almost doubled from 22 to 39. A difference in sampling methodology could have contributed. Naturalised and introduced animals are now included.
- There are two Endangered, three Vulnerable, and five Near threatened species.

Many thanks to those who participated.

KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment - Informal Large Mammal Survey - Period: 1 January - 31 March 2025

Common name		Afrikaans name	Scientific name	Red list status	2010 Census
Aardvark		Erdvark	<i>Orycteropus afer</i>	Least concern	1
Aardwolf		Aardwolf	<i>Proteles cristata</i>	Least concern	1
Baboon, Chacma		Bobbejaan	<i>Papio ursinus</i>	Least concern	1
Blesbok (Re-introduced)	***	Blesbok	<i>Damaliscus pygargus phillipsi</i>	Least concern	1
Bushbuck, Southern		Bosbok	<i>Tragelaphus sylvaticus</i>	Least concern	1
Bushpig		Bosvark	<i>Potamochoerus larvatus</i>	Least concern	
Caracal		Rooikat	<i>Caracal caracal</i>	Least concern	1
Deer, Fallow (Naturalised)		Takbok	<i>Dama dama</i>	Least concern	
Duiker, Common		Duiker	<i>Sylvicapra grimmia</i>	Least concern	1
Fox, Bat-eared		Bakoorjakkals	<i>Otocyon megalotis</i>	Least concern	
Fox, Cape		Draaijakkals, Silwerjakkals	<i>Vulpes chama</i>	Least concern	1
Genet, Large Spotted	***	Grootkolmuskeljaatkat	<i>Genetta maculata</i>	Least concern	
Hare, Scrub		Vlakhaas	<i>Lepus saxatilis</i>	Least concern	
Honey Badger	***	Ratel	<i>Mellivora capensis</i>	Least concern	1
Hyaena, Brown		Strandwolf	<i>Parahyaena brunnea</i>	Near threatened	
Hyrax, Rock		Klipdassie	<i>Procavia capensis</i>	Least concern	
Jackal, Black-backed (Silver-backed)		Rooijakkals, Swartrugjakkals	<i>Canis mesomelas</i>	Least concern	1
Jackal, Side-striped		Grysjakkals, Witwasjakkals	<i>Canis adustus</i>	Least concern	1
Leopard	***	Luiperd	<i>Panthera pardus</i>	Vulnerable	
Mongoose, Slender	***	Rooimuishond	<i>Herpestes sanguineus</i>	Least concern	
Mongoose, Water	***	Kommetjiegatmuishond	<i>Atilax paludinosus</i>	Least concern	
Mongoose, White-tailed	***	Witstertmuishond	<i>Ichneumia albicauda</i>	Least concern	
Mongoose, Yellow		Geelmeerkat, Witkwamuishond	<i>Cynictis penicillata</i>	Least concern	
Monkey, Samango		Samango-aap	<i>Chlorocebus albogularis</i>	Vulnerable	1
Monkey, Vervet		Blou aapie	<i>Chlorocebus pygerythrus</i>	Least concern	1
Oribi		Oorbietjie	<i>Ourebia ourebi ourebi</i>	Endangered	1
Otter, Cape Clawless		Otter	<i>Aonyx capensis</i>	Near threatened	1
Otter, Spotted-necked	***	Klein Otter	<i>Hydrictis maculicollis</i>	Vulnerable	1
Polecat	***	Stinkmuishond	<i>Ictonyx striatus</i>	Least concern	
Porcupine, Cape		Ystervark	<i>Hystrix africae australis</i>	Least concern	
Rabbit, Red Rock		Rooiklipkonyn	<i>Pronolagus crassicaudatus</i>	Least concern	1
Reedbuck, Mountain		Rooiribbok	<i>Redunca fulvorufula fulvorufula</i>	Endangered	1
Reedbuck, Southern		Rietbok	<i>Redunca arundinum</i>	Least concern	
Rhebok, Grey (Common)		Vaal Ribbok	<i>Pelea capreolus</i>	Near threatened	1
Serval		Tierboskat	<i>Leptailurus serval</i>	Near threatened	1
Springbok (Introduced)		Springbok	<i>Antidorcas marsupialis</i>	Least concern	
Steenbok		Steenbok	<i>Raphicerus campestris</i>	Least concern	
Weasel, Striped		Slangmuishond	<i>Poecilogale albinucha</i>	Near threatened	1
Wildcat, African	***	Vaalboskat	<i>Felis silvestris</i>	Least concern	1
Note: *** = only reported by one observer					